

NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING OF STEEL PIPES WITH GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER (GFRP) REPAIRS EXPOSED TO OFFSHORE ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) composite repairs have proven effective for repairing steel pipes due to their excellent mechanical properties and durability. Nonetheless, the aggressiveness of offshore environments can cause degradation on these repaired pipes. Non-destructive testing (NDT) is a reliable approach for assessing the actual repair condition without disassembling the pipeline. This study used two NDT techniques to evaluate damage presence and evolution in steel pipes with FRP systems exposed to offshore environments. The pipes underwent different surface treatments and were conditioned in salt spray chambers at varying temperatures. Results indicated that NDT's effectively detected damage and were consistent with each other.

KEYWORDS

non-destructive testing; aging; pipeline; salt spray

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass Fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composite repairs have been used in steel pipes that transport water, oil, and gas due to their excellent mechanical properties and durability against (Shamsuddoha et al., 2013). aging. FRP repairs consist of a polymer composite bonded to the surface of the steel, with epoxy resin and glass fibers most commonly used materials (Baldan, 2004). Alabtah et al. (2021) discuss the applications of different FRP composites in pipelines and their development over time, including common ways of using FRP composites in different pipeline applications. A detailed review on the hygrothermal aging of steel/FRP pipe repair systems was presented (Vieira et al., 2023). The authors highlight factors that can contribute to the degradation of adhesive properties such as the presence of moisture and temperature near its glass transition temperature (T_g). The roughness of the substrate can also affect the steel/FRP adhesion. The degradation of these pipelines exposed to offshore environments can impair performance and service life, requiring periodic monitoring to prevent premature failures.

One way to inspect the integrity of pipeline repairs without the need to destroy them is through the use of Non-Destructive Testing (NDT). The use of NDT for periodic inspection can ensure the safety of the system, as it has the ability to detect internal and external defects, such as cracks, corrosion, wear and deformations (Hull, 2012; Heslehurst, 2017). Furthermore, it can be used to assess the remaining life of pipelines and determine if repairs or replacements are necessary, thereby avoiding failures and leaks that can cause accidents and environmental damage. In brief, the use of NDT allows for the identification of problems before they become critical, reducing the costs of pipeline repair and maintenance. There are various NDT techniques such as visual inspection, imaging and electromagnetic fields, optical techniques, and acoustic waves (Fu & Yao, 2022). The choice of technique will depend

on factors such as the geometry, physical properties, and materials of the samples (Jolly et al., 2015). In this work, ultrasound and shearography techniques were used as they have great potential for field application.

Shearography is an optical technique that uses laser interferometry to detect surface deformations without the need for contact. The technique uses a laser to produce a holographic image of the object. Then the object is subjected to a small amount of stress (loading), causing it to slightly deform. The laser is used again to produce another holographic image of the material under stress. The two images are compared to detect differences, which may indicate the presence of defects or flaws (de Souza, 2015; Sirohi, 2021). Shearography applications include material characterization, residual stress evaluation, leak detection, vibration studies and 3D shape measurement (Sirohi, 2021, Lee et al., 2004). Shearography has been used to verify the area of defects in fiber-reinforced composites at varying depths and achieved an accuracy between 90-95% compared to the actual value (De Angelis et al., 2012). Yusef et al. (2019) analyzed the identification of faults in an aircraft fairing using Shearography. Their results demonstrated a high concentration of deformation in the region of the faults. Liu et al. (2011) investigated the capability of shearography to detect defects in polymeric and metallic materials using thermal loading. The analyzed defects were of the hole and crack types. The fringe multiplication technique was applied and it was observed that the smallest detectable diameter for a hole defect was 0.8 to 1.3 times its depth. In cracks, the value rises to 2.5 to 3.0 in aluminum plates. The authors also found that the shearing direction of the image has a considerable influence on the sensitivity to detect crack defects.

Ultrasound, on the other hand, is a non-destructive inspection technique that uses high-frequency sound waves, commonly ranging from 500 kHz to 20MHz, to detect imperfections or defects in materials and structures (Hull, 2012). The use of this technique in composite material inspection has been widely studied, having applications in verifying material integrity (Adams & Cawley, 1989), as well as obtaining the elastic properties of the composite (Littles et al., 1998). In addition, it can be used as a reference for other non-destructive techniques (Tamborrino et al., 2016; Palumbo et al., 2016). Berketis et al (2009) used the ultrasound technique with air as a coupling agent to demonstrate that impact-damaged areas do not increase in diameter with degradation generated by aging, achieving perfect visualization of the damaged area through C-Scan images. The author compared several emission frequencies to find that 1MHz produced the best resolution obtained, optimizing the signal-to-noise ratio. The wave velocity in the medium was found to be independent of the generating frequency (Tamborrino et al., 2016), and the reduction of stiffness generated by aging reduces the propagation velocity (Berketis et al., 2009). Despite being widely used and disseminated, the ultrasound technique has limitations such as hidden zones caused by surface delaminations and total signal reflection, which can hide deeper damages (Guillaud et al., 2015).

The present study aims to compare two non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques to evaluate the effects of accelerated aging on samples of metallic pipes with repairs made of fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRP) exposed to a simulated offshore environment.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Specimens

A total of 25 steel pipes repaired with glass fiber reinforced polymer materials were used in this study. Specimens were 4" sch 40 steel with 500 mm in length. The repair occupied 300 mm of the pipe length. These repairs were applied by the same manufacturer and comprise one sample with artificially introduced defects used as a reference, and 24 aged samples without introduced defects. 24 specimens compose 4 groups of 6 pipes with different preparations of the metal surface, namely: manual sanding without silane (L0), machine sanding without silane (M0), manual sanding with silane (LS), and machine sanding with silane (MS). The reference pipe was manufactured using the M0 condition. In the repairs, alternating layers of bidirectional glass reinforcement fabric (type E) were used.

The pipes were divided into 3 hygrothermal salt-spray chambers for accelerated aging in a saline environment manufactured by Equilam. The division was made so that each chamber contained a pair of samples for each surface preparation condition. The temperatures used were 35 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C. The test parameters followed ASTM B117 (19) (G01 Committee, 2019), except for the 55 °C and 70 °C chambers, which were deliberately selected above the proposed standard for experimental purposes. Inside the chambers, in addition to being subjected to temperature, the samples are subjected to a constant salt spray, with a concentration between 4 to 6%, in order to simulate the climatic conditions of an offshore environment. The humidity inside the chambers is 95 to 100% RH. The samples were subjected to the saline condition in the chambers for ~14,000 hours. Ten conditioning periods were carried out, with defined intervals as shown in Table 1. Before the start of conditioning, all samples were inspected in their non-aged condition, referred to as T0. Each period corresponds to a defined aging time between sample removals from their respective chambers to be inspected by Shearography and Ultrasound techniques. The appearance of the pipes in T0 and aged at 55°C and 70°C can be seen in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Pipes in different aging conditions: from left to right – not aged, aged at 55°C and 70°C. It is possible to notice the aggressiveness of accelerated aging.

Table 1 - Summary of conditioning period in hygrothermal chambers

Nomenclature	Time interval (h)	Accumulated (h)
T0	0	0
T1	570	570
T2	1250	1820
T3	1670	3490
T4	1670	5160
T5	1670	6830
T6	1670	8500
T7	1670	10170
T8	1670	11840
T9	1670	13510

In the reference sample, Teflon tapes that simulate defects were inserted along the metal surface (below the composite) with different dimensions and arranged according to the map shown in Fig. 2. The defects had square shapes with sides having 10 mm, 20 mm or 30 mm. The pipe length is on the longitudinal axis and the perimeter represents the circumferential axis.

Figure 3. Shearography test setup during an inspection. The green laser illuminates the surface of the tube that underwent thermal loading and the interferometer causes a lateral shift in the image that is captured by the camera.

Ultrasonic Testing (UT)

Ultrasonic inspections were performed by the team from the Laboratory of Non-Destructive Testing, Corrosion and Welding (LNDC), affiliated with COPPE/UFRJ. For the inspection, a preliminary study was necessary to determine the best settings to be used, including the choice of transducer, shoe geometry (including the water column), water flow, methodology for signal analysis, and other parameters under analysis. Based on this information, a portable setup was developed by the LNDC, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Ultrasonic Setup. Note the displacement of the transducer and water column on the axis of rotation of the tube for scanning and generating the C-Scan.

A direct current motor was used to automate the rotational movement of the tube. The motor was coupled with a reduction box on the tube's rotation axis, with the angular position signal derivation provided by the encoder to the Olympus Omniscan X2 equipment and the development of a microprocessed electronic control circuit for motor operation. In this way, upon the operator's command, the apparatus executes a precise rotation (determined by the desired signal resolution) in synchronism with the angular position measurement of the transducer recorded in the Omniscan for C-scan assembly. The Olympus C539-SM transducer was used with normal incidence and longitudinal wave, with a frequency of 1 MHz. The sweep gain was 14 dB, and water was used as a coupling agent. In order to understand the behavior of the ultrasound signal in the repair region, some points corresponding to the defect-free area in the reference sample were selected and the original A-Scan signal was analyzed. For the analysis of all samples, the original C-Scan was obtained directly from the

Omniscan. For a more detailed analysis, Matlab software (version 2018) was used to select the signals of interest. From the initial reading in Matlab, the signals of interest were chosen, binarized, and the regions with characteristics associated with discontinuities were identified.

Composite material and steel have different acoustic impedance values, but this difference is not so simple to detect in the reflection of the signal since the signal from the steel can mask the signal from the composite. When there are defects in the steel-composite interface, a thin layer of air is formed. Air has a higher acoustic impedance value compared to composite/steel values. The change in the order of acoustic impedances causes a phase inversion (polarity of the echo) in defective regions. This phase inversion was detected by the ultrasound equipment indicating the presence of a defective interface.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Qualitative analysis

In order to estimate the performance of the NDTs, an inspection of the reference sample containing artificially inserted defects was carried out. Fig. 5 shows the result of the techniques in relation to the expected standard. The standard mapping was made according to the position of the teflon tapes inserted below the composite and is represented by the empty squares with black borders. Shearography is represented by the gray color and ultrasound by the checkered pattern. The result in terms of the number of detections was 83.3% for shearography and 50% for ultrasound. This result is important to understand how the technique behaves in inspections on this type of sample, as well as its limitations and advantages. In this case, it is possible to verify that both techniques are capable of inspecting the proposed samples.

Figure 5: Evaluation of NDT's. The map helps in the correlation between the techniques. It is observed that Shearography detected more defects (teflon tapes) than ultrasound.

Quantitative analysis

In this stage, the evolution of the degraded area in the pipes was quantitatively analyzed by shearography (SH) and ultrasound (UT) techniques. The average damaged area of the 24 pipes was calculated, as summarized in table 2. The pipes that did not present defects were removed from the calculation of the average in order to improve the dispersion. However, the high dispersion values can be justified by the amount of samples used, since each hygrothermal chamber had 8 pipes with 4 different surface treatments.

Table 2: Average defect area

Nomenclature	Accumulated (h)	Shearography		Ultrasound	
		Average (mm ²)	S.D. (mm ²)	Average (mm ²)	S.D. (mm ²)
T0	0	1970	4753	10616	7240
T1	570	2742	6219	16634	8851
T2	1820	3747	8475	18842	9917
T3	3490	8587	18791	18950	9973
T4	5160	9255	20259	20272	10674
T5	6830	11062	25337	20322	10683
T6	8500	11062	25337	20382	10661
T7	10170	11182	25435	20382	10661
T8	11840	11182	25435	20382	10661
T9	13510	11182	25435	20490	10575

Defects found in pre-conditioning (T0) are related to the rolling process, where delamination [8] or lack of adhesive can occur. The shearography technique detected defects in 10 pipes from the first inspection. It is interesting to note that, according to shearography, pipes without initial defects did not show indications of damage until T9. Of the 10 pipes with initial defects, only 4 showed an evolution of the damaged area, with one of them reaching the aging plateau already at time T1, two others between T2-T5, and finally one pipe at T7.

The ultrasound technique detected defects in all pipes from the first inspection, and almost all presented an aging plateau between T4-T5. This difference in detection quantity may be influenced by the inspection methodology adopted. The phase inversion methodology was used to overcome the difficulties in reading the reflected signal in the region of interest. However, this solution still requires further studies. Ultrasound is well established as a non-destructive technique, but its application in composite-steel samples still needs to be further investigated.

In Fig. 6a, it can be observed that the average degradation value did not exceed 30% of the useful area of the repair, which is 108000 mm². In addition, the first aging times show greater growth in the damaged areas with a tendency towards stability after T5.

Figure 6: Defect areas (%)

In figures 6-b-d, the graphs of the average damaged area were plotted to visualize the influence of temperature on material aging. It was observed that at a temperature of 70 °C, there was a significant increase in the detection of damaged areas, as expected, since as the temperature increases, the remaining properties of the material decrease. In this case, ultrasound showed a slight decrease in detection compared to other temperatures, and shearography detected larger defect areas, deviating from the results for 35 °C and 55 °C. However, it was observed that this specific increase in shearography was influenced by two pipes conditioned in the 70 °C chamber, as can be seen in figures 7-a,b. These pipes were conditioned in the same hygrothermal chamber and have different surface treatments, M0 and MS. However, no significant relationship was observed between surface treatments and the progression of aging for other pipes.

Figure 7: Comparison defect areas (%)

CONCLUSION

In general, the techniques were satisfactory in evaluating the presence and evolution of damages in steel pipes with FRP exposed to offshore environments. Regarding the advantages, both techniques have good repeatability and potential for application. Shearography has good productivity and has shown to be mature for field application. However, it has a low availability of service providers. Ultrasonography has wide availability of service providers, as it is well established among NDTs, and the need for adjustment in the methodology used, to avoid false positives, becomes attractive for the development of new methodologies. As future work, the authors suggest the validation of inspection techniques through sample dissection. From the destructive test, it will be possible to determine the level of assertiveness of the techniques used in this work.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.